

Notes

A Study of Complex Formation of Some Thiophene Derivatives with Metal Ions.

Part I

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Manuscript received 27 November 1972; revised 8 April 1974;
accepted 30 April 1974

LIGANDS containing both soft and hard donor atoms as well as simple carboxylate ions are investigated to examine their interaction with both types of soft and hard metal ion acids. With this in view, thiophene-2-carboxylic acid(I), tetrahydrothiophene-2-carboxylic acid (II), acetic acid(III), *m*-nitrobenzoic acid(IV) and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid(V) were used as ligands, while copper(II), cadmium(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) ions were used as cations. Among these metal ions cadmium(II) is definitely a soft acid¹ and other have mixed soft and hard character. The present study is intended to investigate into any metal-sulphur interaction in the complexes. M-S π interaction and its effect on formation constants of the complexes has been a matter of interesting study by Suzuki and Yamasaki², Bhattacharye and coworkers³, Irving and Fernelius⁴ and many others. Ligand(II) has been prepared by hydrogenating I, whereby the aromatic character of the ring is removed. This is done to activate the sulphur to become a better donor. A few more non-chelating ligands III, IV and V containing oxygen as donor atom are also included for comparison. Also on survey of literature it is found that no work is done on ligands IV and V. The experimental method consists of Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique⁵ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶. Although some studies on stabilities of acetate complexes in aqueous medium⁷ and cupric ion complexes of I, II and III in aqueous dioxan medium⁸ have been reported, comprehensive data are not available. We are interested in the possibility that the ligands I and II might act as bidentate ligands when entering into complex formation with the metal ions. Such chelation would be expected to result in greater stabilities for these complexes than would be predicted from the basicities of the carboxylate anions. The formation constants are also expected to have some relation to the soft and hard character of the metal ions.

Experimental

Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid was received from Fluka AG. Tetrahydro-2-carboxylic acid was prepared by reducing thiophene-2-carboxylic acid with

2.5% sodium amalgam as described by Putokhin and Egorova⁹. From the final water solution the acid was recovered by extraction with benzene. Its melting point was found to be 49.5° (reported 53°^{9a} and 51°^{9a}). Dioxan (B.D.H., A.R.) was further purified¹⁰ by standard method and its b.p. was 99°/750 mm (reported¹⁰ 101°/760 mm) *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (England) was recrystallised thrice from water (m.p. 138°). *o*-chlorobenzoic acid was recrystallised twice from water (m.p. 137°). All other chemicals were of A.R. or G.R. quality.

Perchlorates of nickel and cadmium were prepared by treating a solution of perchloric acid of requisite strength with excess of their hydroxides and diluting the solution to a suitable volume. Zinc perchlorate was prepared by neutralising an amount of zinc oxide exactly equivalent to 0.04M perchloric acid and diluting to the required volume. Cupric salt hydrolyses at pH \approx 6^{11(a)}, therefore cupric-perchlorate is prepared by dissolving an amount of cupric oxide exactly equivalent to 10 ml of approximately 1.6M perchloric acid in 20 ml of acid and diluting this to 100 ml. This gives 0.08M cupric perchlorate solution. Cadmium and nickel were estimated by standard methods. A Cambridge bench type pH meter was used for pH measurements. The meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 6.98 and 4.01 at 30°.

All titrations were carried out in a 250ml beaker kept in a water thermostat maintained at 30° \pm 0.1° Nitrogen atmosphere is maintained by bubbling nitrogen gas (previously saturated with the solvent) throughout the experiment. Thirty five to forty five readings were taken in each case (except in case of blank titration, where 10-14 readings were required) and the time required for this was about 1 hr. \pm 10 mins. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible data. The metal/ligand ratio was maintained at about 1 : 5.

Blank titration : A mixture of 1.0 ml 0.1M HClO₄, 4.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄, 20 ml of dioxan and 15 ml of water (to make the total volume 40 in all titrations) was titrated by 0.2M NaOH until the pH rises to about 11.

Ligand titration : In general, a mixture of 1 ml of 0.1M HClO₄; 4.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄; 5.0 ml of 0.04M ligand; 20 ml of dioxan and 10 ml of water was used in each titration.

Metal titrations : A mixture of 5.0 ml of 0.04M ligand, 1.0 ml of 0.04M metal perchlorate solution (in case of copper, 0.5 ml of 0.08M cupric perchlorate solution was taken), 1.0 ml of 0.1M HClO₄, 4 ml of 1M NaClO₄, 20 ml of dioxan and water to make up the volume 40 ml, was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

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Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constants for the acids are calculated with the help of \bar{n}_A values (the mean number of protons bound per ligand ion) at different B values (pH meter reading in aqueous-dioxan medium). \bar{n}_A is calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁶ as adopted by Jabalpurwala *et. al.*¹¹. Plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. From this straight line the value of the practical dissociation constant was obtained using the relation¹²

$$\log {}^pK_1^{H-} = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$$

These values are given in Table 1. For metal ligand stability constants \bar{n} and pL were calculated following the method of Jabalpurwala *et al.*¹¹. The values of \bar{n} are plotted against pL . The curves do not show distinctive separation of steps. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values calculated by half integral method are found to be very close (differing by less than 2 in log units). So least squares method is employed to calculate the constants. Some of the values are recalculated by the method of Block and McIntyre¹³. These values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 2—THE ORDER OF STABILITIES OF METAL COMPLEXES WITH THE LIGANDS

Ligands	Order of stability for 1 : 1 Complexes	
I	Cd \approx Cu > Ni > Zn	
II	Cu > Ni \approx Cd > Zn	
III	Cu > Ni > Zn > Cd	
IV	Zn > Cu > Ni > Cd	
V	Cu > Zn > Ni	

In the present work we found Ni > Zn for ligands I, II and III. For sulphur containing ligands Williams¹⁵ suggested two orders Ni > Zn for uncharged sulphur and Zn > Ni for charged sulphur. For the ligand I and II the sulphur is not charged. And that explains the order for these ligands. Cadmium on account of its much greater ionic radius than zinc (Cd—0.96Å; Zn 0.72Å) and much smaller second ionisation potential (Cd—599.9 KCal/mole, Zn—633.5 Kcal/

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES AT 30.0±0.1°C IN 50% V/V WATER-DIOXAN MEDIUM WITH 0.1M

Ligands	Proton ligand stability constant	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)		Cd(II)	
		log K ₁	log K ₂						
T2CA	4.98 (5.0) ^a	3.27 (2.91)	—	2.63 (1.85)	—	2.15 (2.05)	—	3.29	—
THT-2-CA	5.25 (5.58)	4.10 (4.31)	3.44 [3.56]	3.00	—	2.34 [2.43]	3.16 [3.17]	2.98 [2.93]	3.08 [2.97]
Acetic acid	6.00 (6.01)	3.32 (3.36)	3.04	2.91	—	2.57	2.55	2.11	—
m Nitrobenzoic acid	4.83	2.52 [2.71]	3.61 [3.51]	2.49 [2.38]	2.72 [2.84]	2.84	—	2.21 [2.24]	3.51 [3.47]
o-Chlorobenzoic acid	4.75	2.88	—	2.01 [2.40]	3.49 [3.29]	2.81	—	—	—

^a Values in the first bracket are those reported⁹ at 25° in 50% V/V Water-Dioxan medium with 0.1M NaClO,

^b Values in the third bracket are those obtained by the method of Block and McIntyre.

From the Table 2, we find that in cases of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes Irving Williams order Ni < Cu > Zn is not violated except in case of ligand IV in the strictest sense of the term. Ni and Zn being both less than Cu in the order. It appears that in most of the high spin complexes Ni > Zn. Out of 49 examples cited in Irving and Williams' paper¹⁴ there is only a single case with thiosulphate ion as ligand, where Ni < Zn.

mole) is expected to come much later in the stability sequence. But for ligands I and II cadmium occupies high places in the stability order. On hydrogenation aromaticity of the T2CA is removed. This has the effect of diminishing the acidic character of the acid, and so the $\log {}^pK_1^{H-}$ has increased from 4.98 to 5.25. This increase in basicity has its effect on the general increase of stabilities of metal complexes with this ligand.

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With T2CA(I) cadmium complex is more stable than copper. This may be explained on the basis of M-S π interaction between the ligand and cadmium ion soft acid¹. As N.M.R.⁹ studies indicate at least partial interaction of the sulphur of I with copper, a stronger M-S π interaction and therefore some amount of chelation with this ligand with cadmium may be inferred. This can also be adjudged from the basicities of the other ligands and the stabilities of their (1:1) complexes with cadmium.

With TH2CA(II) copper gives the most stable complex for both 1:1 and 1:2 cases, The log K_2 value is also quite high. Considering the basicities of other ligands and the corresponding stabilities it may be said that copper has chelated with this ligand. Cadmium classified as a strong soft acid¹ did not form a stronger complex than copper as was expected from the enhanced donor power of the sulphur in ligand II. This shows that possibly a strong α bond with copper prevails over the M-S π back donated bond with cadmium. The log K_2 values with copper, cadmium and zinc indicate 1:2 complex formation. An interesting feature with this ligand is that log $K_2 > \log K_1$ for zinc and cadmium. Such reverse statistical effects were observed by Irving and Fernelius⁴ with complexes between sulphur containing ligands, *S*-ethylmercaptopropionic acid, *o*-(*S*-ethyl) mercaptobenzoic acid and metal ions like Cd(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II). Although no explanation was offered for these results, it appears that M-S π interaction plays some significant role in these cases. The above argument can be advanced to explain the reversal of successive stabilities for cadmium and zinc. It may be concluded, therefore, that there is a trend towards bis-chelation for copper cadmium and zinc with ligand II.

For copper, nickel and cadmium complexes of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid again we find, log $K_2 > \log K_1$. The number of systems where log $K_{n+1} < \log K_n$ is limited. This is observed in case of silver amines⁶⁻⁹, zinc amines²⁰, Fe(II)-*o*-phenanthroline^{21,22}, Fe(II) dipyriddy²³ and a number of sulphur containing ligands²⁴. For zinc amines the reason is stated to be due to the change from weakly coordinated octahedral Zn²⁺(H₂O)₆ to strongly coordinated tetrahedral Zn²⁺L₄ complex.²⁵ Similar explanation is given for Ag-amines. In case of Fe(II) *o*-phenanthroline and Fe(II) dipyriddy successive stability constants are larger because the tris-complex is diamagnetic and when this is formed from the mono or bis-complexes, which are aquated, high spin state changes to low spin state. Such explanations are not tenable for the *m*-nitrobenzoic acid complexes. One explanation may be intramolecular hydrogen-bonding between the oxygen of the nitrogroup and the oxygen of the aquated complexes. There may also be other reasons. More work, however is needed to explain this. Similar effect log $K_2 > \log K_1$ is also observed with nickel complex of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid.

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